

Thermodynamic study of Ar + Kr mixture using ultrasonic velocity and density[†]

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Abstract : Ultrasonic velocity and density data have been employed to compute a number of thermodynamic properties (α , β_T , ρ , β_S , C_P , C_V , V^E , P_1 , γ , Γ etc.) of Ar + Kr mixture of 120 K, 130 K and 140 K on the basis of Flory's statistical theory. Quite satisfactory agreement is found for those properties whose experimental values are known. Recently developed empirical relations for α and β_T in terms of ρ and u are applied to Ar + Kr mixture as well as pure Ar and Kr. These relations fail to account the thermodynamic properties of Ar + Kr.

Keywords : Thermodynamics, Ar + Kr mixture, ultrasonic velocity, density.

Introduction

Stavely *et al.*¹ measured the vapour pressure and density of Ar + Kr system, and evaluated the excess volume V^E and excess free energy G^E over the whole composition range at 115.77 K. They found that G^E and H^E were positive with $G^E \approx H^E$. The excess volume was found to be negative and fairly large at this temperature. Lattice theories with corresponding states principle failed to account the excess properties of Ar + Kr mixture. Flory and Hocker² related the excess properties of the mixture with the measurable macroscopic properties of the pure components Ar and Kr. On this basis they obtained encouraging results for V^E , G^E , H^E and TS^E . For this purpose they applied the most important and useful theory developed by Flory and coworkers^{3,4}. In the present work we have undertaken the study Ar + Kr system from entirely different approach. We are employing acoustic velocity and density values for the investigating this system. In earlier papers^{5,6} from this laboratory, Flory's statistical theories have been extended for computing ultrasonic velocity and a number of other important and useful thermodynamic properties of pure liquids, binary

and multicomponent mixtures. We may mention some of our recent papers^{7,8}. It appears from literature that nobody has succeeded in applying these theories to Ar + Kr system due to nonavailability of acoustic velocity data. After an exhaustive literature survey it has been found that accurate measurements of velocity and density of this system were carried out by Blagoi *et al.*⁹ at different temperatures. In the present work we have employed their data for estimating a number of useful and important thermodynamic properties of Ar + Kr system using various approaches.

The most widely employed Flory's statistical theory^{3,4} has been extended to binary and multicomponent liquid mixture for calculating theoretically the ultrasonic velocity, density, surface tension and other thermodynamic properties. It is worthwhile to mention few latest references⁵⁻⁸. Here we are applying this theory to obtain theoretically a number of thermodynamic properties related to density and ultrasonic velocity for Ar + Kr system. Another approach has also been employed to calculate the values of thermal expansivity (α) and isothermal compressibility (β_T) from the density (ρ) and acoustic

[†]In honour of Professor M. C. Chattopadhyaya on the occasion of his 70th birth anniversary.

velocity (u) data. On the dimension basis empirical relations for calculating α and β_T from ρ and u data were derived for the first time in our laboratory¹⁰. These relations have been used by several workers¹¹⁻¹⁶ to obtain the values of α and β_T in case of different types of liquid systems (pure and mixtures). Recently, Marcus has also highlighted those relations in his review¹⁷.

Theoretical :

The familiar equations of Flory theory have been given in detail in our earlier papers⁵⁻⁷. Briefly we are summarizing these equations under the following lines :

$$\alpha = \frac{3(\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1)}{T(1 - 3(\tilde{V}^{1/3} - 1))} \quad (1)$$

$$\beta_T = \frac{\alpha T \tilde{V}^2}{P^*} \quad (2)$$

$$V^E = (\sum x_i V_i^*) \tilde{V}^E \quad (3)$$

$$P_i = \frac{\alpha T}{\beta_T} \quad (4)$$

$$\rho = \frac{x_1 M_1 + x_2 M_2}{(x_1 V_1^* + x_2 V_2^*) \tilde{V}} \quad (5)$$

$$C_p = (x_1 C_{p,1} + x_2 C_{p,2}) + C_p^E \quad (6)$$

$$u = \left(\frac{1}{\beta_S \rho} \right)^{1/2} \quad (7)$$

$$\beta_S = \beta_T - \frac{\alpha^2 T V}{C_p} \quad (8)$$

$$\gamma = \beta_T / \beta_S \quad (9)$$

$$C_V = C_p / \gamma \quad (10)$$

$$\Gamma = \frac{\gamma - 1}{\alpha_T} \quad (11)$$

where all the symbols have their usual notations as described earlier^{5,6}.

On the basis of dimensional analysis, relationships for thermal expansivity, α , and isothermal compressibility, β_T , in terms of density, ρ , and ultrasonic velocity, u ,

have been obtained during recent past¹⁰. These relations present permit the estimation of α and β_T from ρ and u data. These relations have been applied to pure liquids and liquid mixtures¹¹⁻¹⁶ successfully, and given by

$$\alpha_{Exp} = \frac{75.6 \times 10^{-3}}{T^{1/9} u^{1/2} \rho^{1/3}}, \text{ K}^{-1} \quad (12)$$

$$\beta_{T (Exp)} = \frac{1.71 \times 10^{-3}}{T^{4/9} \rho^{4/3} u^2}, \text{ cm}^2 \text{ dyne}^{-1} \quad (13)$$

where u is in m sec^{-1} and ρ in g cm^{-3} .

Using above equations and relevant thermodynamic relations, expressions for γ , P_{int} , and pseudo-Gruneisen parameter, Γ , can be derived and result is

$$\gamma = \frac{17.1}{T^{4/9} \rho^{1/3}} \quad (14)$$

$$P_{int} = 44.2 T^{4/3} u^{3/2} \rho \quad (15)$$

General formulation for the non-linearity parameter in terms of the acoustical parameters of liquids has been made using the expression for the sound velocity (u), and introducing the contribution due to isobaric acoustic parameters (K) and the isothermal acoustic parameter (K''). The expression for the calculation of B/A of mixture has been expressed as¹⁸

$$\frac{B}{A} = 2K + 2\gamma K'' \quad (16)$$

Computations of K and K'' require only the knowledge of thermal expansion coefficient, α . Detailed method of calculation is given in literature^{19,20}.

Results and discussion

Table 1 enlists the experimental properties of pure components Ar and Kr at three different temperatures 120 K, 130 K and 140 K taken from literature¹⁰. The recorded properties include density (ρ), molar volume (V), ultrasonic velocity (u), adiabatic compressibility (β_T) and thermal expansivity (α). Table 2 records the calculated values of a number of important and useful thermodynamic properties (α , β_T , ρ , β_S , C_p , C_V , V^E , P_i , γ , Γ , C_p^E , u and B/A) for Ar + Kr mixture, using Flory's theory from eqs. (1) to (11), at 120 K, 130 K and 140 K. Experimental values of u , β_S and ρ for the mixture and their percentage deviations alongwith average percentage deviation (APD) from Flory values are presented in Table

Table 1. Parameters of pure components at different temperatures

Component	T (K)	V ($\text{cm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)	u (m s^{-1})	$\beta_S \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{dyne}^{-1}$)	ρ (g cm^{-3})	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (K^{-1}) (Exp)	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{dyne}^{-1}$) (Exp)	\tilde{V}	T^*	P^* (J cm^{-3})	C_p ($\text{J mol}^{-1} \text{K}^{-1}$)
Argon	120	34.15	585.0	252	1.1595	7.8	700	1.5656	1353.62	327.74	54
Kr	120	34.80	684.0	87	2.4568	3.3	172	1.3113	1821.56	395.91	47
Argon	130	37.31	487.7	392	1.0725	11.5	1300	1.7268	1348.44	342.93	63
Kr	130	35.92	642.0	109	2.2259	3.4	208	1.3389	1877.61	380.94	50
Argon	140	42.70	369.9	769	0.9504	24.0	3800	1.9856	1360.11	348.59	92
Kr	140	37.25	600.0	122	2.2769	3.8	282	1.3890	1874.43	363.97	53

Table 2. Computed values of thermodynamic properties of Ar + Kr mixture at various temperatures by Flory theory

x_1	V^E	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (K^{-1})	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{dyne}^{-1}$)	$\beta_S \times 10^{12}$ ($\text{cm}^2 \text{dyne}^{-1}$)	C_p ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	$P_i \times 10^{-7}$ (dyne cm^{-2})	C_p^E	ρ (g cm^{-3})	γ	u (m s^{-1})	Γ	C_v ($\text{J K}^{-1} \text{mol}^{-1}$)	B/A
Ar + Kr at 120 K													
0.8	-0.6195	5.987	458.77	170.56	50.24	156.61	-2.3571	1.4474	2.6898	636.46	2.3519	18.68	9.729
0.6	-0.7854	4.912	332.42	131.02	48.34	177.32	-2.8604	1.7098	2.5371	668.13	2.6078	19.05	9.160
0.5	-0.7562	4.524	290.37	117.04	47.78	186.97	-2.7209	1.8350	2.4809	682.36	2.7279	19.26	8.941
0.4	-0.6730	4.201	256.94	105.60	47.40	196.21	-2.4042	1.9565	2.4333	695.72	2.8429	19.48	8.752
0.2	-0.3887	3.691	207.26	88.04	47.02	213.72	-1.3839	2.1887	2.3541	720.38	3.0570	19.97	8.432
Ar + Kr at 130 K													
0.8	-1.3216	7.438	683.91	203.29	53.44	141.39	-6.9600	1.3643	3.3643	600.46	2.4450	15.88	11.399
0.6	-1.5785	5.623	448.13	160.72	50.30	163.11	-7.5049	1.6344	2.7884	617.01	2.4467	18.04	9.909
0.5	-1.4811	5.047	380.12	145.90	49.67	172.60	-6.8322	1.7611	2.6052	623.83	2.4467	19.06	9.443
0.4	-1.2875	4.593	329.12	133.74	49.39	181.41	-5.8149	1.8830	2.4608	630.14	2.4468	20.07	9.081
0.2	-0.7134	3.909	257.27	114.70	49.45	197.55	-3.1482	2.1145	2.2430	642.13	2.4458	22.05	8.548
Ar + Kr at 140 K													
0.8	-3.5177	9.545	1081.47	154.29	52.40	123.56	-31.8021	1.2790	7.0096	711.88	4.4974	7.48	18.822
0.6	-3.6970	6.543	626.11	167.18	48.09	146.30	-28.3103	1.5612	3.7451	618.97	2.9968	12.84	11.923
0.5	-3.3003	5.791	523.55	165.94	48.16	154.87	-24.3420	1.6871	3.1551	597.66	2.6579	15.26	10.685
0.4	-2.7468	5.239	451.73	162.75	48.78	162.36	-19.8233	1.8063	2.7756	583.23	2.4208	17.57	9.896
0.2	-1.4143	4.430	352.92	152.96	50.74	175.73	-10.0621	2.0319	2.3072	567.22	2.1077	21.99	8.934

3. Quite satisfactory agreement between theoretical and experimental values of u , β_S and ρ for the Ar + Kr mixture has been achieved at all the temperature. It is clear from Table 3 that the average percentage deviation for density is around 1% or below it. This is an excellent agreement. Thus, Flory theory is found to be successful in predicting the thermodynamic properties of Ar + Kr mixture. Since the experimental values of other calculated properties (β_T , C_p , C_v , P_i , γ , Γ etc.) are not available, no comparison could be made. Trend of variation to be satisfactory.

Lastly we have tried to calculate α , β_T , P_{int} and γ for pure Ar and Kr, as well as their mixture from the empiri-

cal eqs. (12) to (15), obtained during recent past, from ρ and u values. Table 4 records the calculated values of α , β_T , P_{int} and γ for pure liquids Ar and Kr at different temperatures. From the percentage deviations of α , β_T , P_{int} and γ values it appears that empirical eqs. (12) to (15) fail completely to account the thermodynamic behaviour of pure Ar and Kr. These equations are further applied to Ar + Kr mixture for computing the values of α , β_T , P_{int} and γ at 120 K, 130 K and 140 K. Since the percentage deviations are high so we do not report these values here. It appears that these relations can not account the thermodynamic properties at low temperatures in case of Ar and Kr.

Table 3. Experimental values of u , ρ and β_S for Ar + Kr mixture alongwith percentage deviation from Flory theory

x_1	u (m s ⁻¹) (Exp)	$\beta_S \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹) (Exp)	ρ (g cm ⁻³) (Exp)	% deviation		
				u	ρ	β_S
Ar + Kr at 120 K						
0.8	610	187	1.4410	-4.34	-0.44	8.79
0.6	640	144	1.7024	-4.40	-0.43	9.01
0.5	652	129	1.8258	-4.66	-0.51	9.27
0.4	664	116	1.9500	-4.78	-0.33	8.97
0.2	679	99	2.1843	-6.09	-0.20	11.07
			APD	4.85	0.38	9.42
Ar + Kr at 130 K						
0.8	537	256	1.3575	-11.82	-0.51	20.59
0.6	581	183	1.6213	-6.20	-0.81	12.18
0.5	596	161	1.7430	-4.67	-1.04	9.38
0.4	611	143	1.8665	-3.13	-0.89	6.47
0.2	630	120	2.0987	-1.93	-0.75	4.42
			APD	5.55	0.80	10.61
Ar + Kr at 140 K						
0.8	458	377	1.2671	-55.43	-0.94	59.08
0.6	517	241	1.5759	-19.72	0.93	30.63
0.5	540	206	1.6723	-10.68	-0.89	19.45
0.4	563	156	1.7721	-3.59	-1.93	-4.33
0.2	582	141	2.0251	2.54	-0.34	-8.49
			APD	18.39	1.00	24.39

Table 4. Calculated values of α , β_T , P_i and γ for pure components using eqs. (12) to (15) alongwith percentage deviation

Component	T (K)	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (K ⁻¹) (Exp)	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹) (Exp)	$P_i \times 10^7$ (dyne cm ⁻²) (Exp)	γ (Exp)	$\alpha \times 10^3$ (K ⁻¹) by eq. (12)	$\beta_T \times 10^{12}$ (cm ² dyne ⁻¹) by eq. (13)	$P_i \times 10^7$ (dyne cm ⁻²) by eq. (15)	γ by eq. (14)	% devi.			
										α	β_T	P_i	γ
Argon	120	7.8	700	133.71	2.78	1.748	488.53	42.92	1.94	77.59	30.21	67.90	30.21
Kr	120	3.3	172	230.23	1.98	1.258	131.31	114.98	1.51	61.86	23.65	50.06	23.65
Argon	130	11.5	1300	115.00	3.32	1.947	752.69	33.62	1.92	83.07	42.10	70.76	42.10
Kr	130	3.4	208	212.50	1.91	1.331	164.08	105.39	1.51	60.87	21.12	50.40	21.12
Argon	140	24.0	3800	88.42	4.94	2.309	1487.49	21.72	1.93	90.38	60.86	75.43	60.86
Kr	140	3.8	282	188.65	2.31	1.355	176.36	107.52	1.45	64.35	37.46	43.01	37.46

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